

Climate Change and Solution

A Review Paper By,

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The term 'Climate Change' denotes long-term shifts in temperature and weather patterns—a process that unfolds over extended periods. While climate change can arise naturally, triggered by changes in the sun's activity or volcanic eruptions, since the industrial revolution, human activities have emerged as the primary catalyst for this phenomenon (Source: United Nations) . Human-induced

alterations in the natural order involve the release of greenhouse gases into the atmosphere, generating additional heat. These gases, predominantly emitted through human activities such as the combustion of fossil fuels, deforestation, and land use changes, have tangible effects on the environment. Notable consequences include the shrinking of glaciers and ice sheets, earlier breakup of rivers and lakes, shifts in plant and animal geographic ranges, and altered blooming patterns.

As scientists predicted, the impacts of global climate change are becoming increasingly evident, manifesting in sea ice loss, accelerated sea-level rise, and

heightened occurrences of heatwaves. Notably, the average world temperature, which was 13.74°C in the 1990s, continued to rise to 13.98°C in the 1950s and 14.51°C in the 2000s (Source: currentresults.com). The trend escalated in 2010, with the temperature reaching 14.63°C, marking that decade as the hottest in recorded history. In 2005, it was noted as the hottest year in 131 years of record-keeping (Source: earthpolicy.org). As of 2023, the temperature stands 1.40°C higher than the preindustrial age (1850-1900), with September recording an average temperature of 16.38°C (Source: Copernicus climate change services). Projections indicate that if current trends

persist, the temperature could rise by 2°C in the next century (Source: currentresults.com).

To combat these challenges, scientists are actively engaged in projects aimed at mitigating climate change. Various technologies are being explored, including:

1. Carbon capture
2. Feeding cows seaweed
3. Utilizing delicious insects
4. Climate repair
5. Promoting remote working
6. Enhancing the use of data entries
7. Improving household energy efficiency

(Source: Sky News)

Among these, Carbon Capture emerges as a prominent and widely accepted strategy to reduce climate change impacts. Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage (CCUS) involves capturing CO₂ from significant sources like power generation or industrial facilities and transporting it for various applications. This technology proves effective in addressing emissions in hard-to-abate sectors, particularly cement, steel, or chemicals. Additionally, CCUS contributes to the broader decarbonization of industries such as transportation and can potentially remove CO₂ from the air to offset challenging-to-abate emissions (Source: International Energy Agency). Notably, successful implementations of

CCUS are observed in the USA, Canada, and Australia (Source: [blog.verde](#)).

In conclusion, industrialization stands out as the primary driver of climate change, emphasizing the critical role of technology, particularly Carbon Capture, in addressing and mitigating its far-reaching consequences.